

LABOR PROTECTION WHEN WORKING AT HEIGHTS

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ANNOTATION. In the article, the importance of organizing workplace safety at heights in the development of industrial production sectors is discussed, highlighting the increasing need for construction, production, and industry in Uzbekistan today. The article also analyzes accidents at heights in construction and industrial enterprises.

KEY WORDS AND PHRASES: working at height, ensuring safety, organizing labor protection, providing instructions, rest regime, proper work analysis, safety belts, and barriers.

INTRODUCTION. Humanity is living in a rapidly developing information age. The organization of the labor protection service is crucial. The arrangement of work on labor protection in enterprises when working at height is carried out in accordance with the model regulation 'On the Organization of Work on Labor Protection' (August 14, 1996, list number No. 273) [1]. According to its status, the labor protection service is considered equal to the main services of the enterprise and is subordinated to its head or relevant responsible employees. It is dissolved in the event of the completion of the enterprise's activities. Employees of the labor protection service, engaged in work at height in enterprises, cannot be involved in performing other duties according to their job instructions.

The study and documentation of accidents and other injuries that occurred in enterprises in connection with labor activities, as approved by the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 286 of June 6, 1997,

'Accidents that Occurred in Production,' and other injuries should be carried out in accordance with the regulation on studying and keeping records (Collection of Decisions of the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 1997, No. 6, Article 21) [2].

The monitoring of employees' health in enterprises must be implemented according to the order of the Minister of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 6, 2000, No. 300, titled 'On improving the system of initial and periodic medical examination of employees in the Republic of Uzbekistan' (June 23, 2000, list number #937; Bulletin of regulatory documents, 2000, No. 12).

MAIN PART. There are dangerous and harmful factors associated with working at heights. Employees should follow the established procedure for their professions and types of work, which includes studying, receiving guidance, passing knowledge tests, and undergoing professional technical training [3].

Measures aimed at protecting against the effects of dangerous and harmful factors during work at heights are crucial. A list of these factors is compiled, considering specific production conditions at each enterprise. For instance, auxiliary equipment such as ladders, platforms, and other devices may be defective in construction. Risks include objects falling from heights, tools, materials, and high levels of slippage due to factors such as freezing, wetting, and lubrication of surfaces like the ground, floor, basin, drain, and other additional equipment. This extends to hazards posed by moving special motor vehicles, moving mechanisms, goods, and other materials. The following provides examples of the aforementioned risks

Appropriate changes should be made to the list in the case of changes in technological processes or introduction of new production equipment that lead to the appearance of new harmful substances or the reduction of the level of exposure to dangerous and harmful factors.

PERSONAL PROTECTIVE EQUIPMENT. Employee protective equipment is crucial for safeguarding employees from harmful and dangerous factors within the production environment. This protection is ensured through the use of modern personal protective equipment in accordance with the requirements of relevant standards for worker safety.

Enterprises are responsible for providing workers and employees with personal protective equipment following established procedures. Those using protective equipment, with knowledge about its use, protective properties, and validity period, should undergo training on proper usage.

Workers are required to use restraint belts when engaged in short-term work

that doesn't allow for the installation of barriers at height. A worker who is not occupied with other tasks and is prepared to provide emergency assistance should be present at the worksite. This worker should have a belt with a retaining hook and nails (in the case of work on a wooden board). Additionally, shoulder straps and hip straps with belts must be in place. Belts should be variable in length, designed to cover the waist of the body from 640 mm to 1500 mm. The width of the belt should not be less than 50 mm, and the width of the belt without a belt should also not be less than 50 mm, with the width of the belt not being less than 80 mm [5].

The materials used for the belt and its shock absorber must withstand a load with a static breaking weight of not less than 7000 N (700 kg). The mass of the belt must endure the dynamic weight of a 100 kg load, equivalent to two maximum lengths of the belt strap during a fall from height. The belt's spring-loaded buckle should enable quick and secure one-handed fastening and unfastening, even when wearing thick gloves. In this case, the duration of tightening and loosening of the spring hook should not exceed three seconds.

The spring-loaded hinge must be equipped with a storage device that prevents unexpected opening situations. The force required to open the spring-loaded hinge should be not less than 30 N (3 kg) and not more than 80 N (8 kg). The spring-loaded hinge should close automatically. Each belt should have its own marking. Every six months, during the use of the working belt, before the next use, each belt should undergo testing at a static load equal to 2250 N (225 kg), and the date of the next test should be marked on the area designated for the marking [5].

If safety belts lack lashing straps, it is necessary to use safety ropes. When performing work at heights, workers must be provided with special anti-slip shoes and a protective helmet.

SAFETY REQUIREMENTS IN THE PERFORMANCE OF WORKS.

The organization of the workplace and work at height should aim to exclude dangerous and harmful production factors for workers. The workplace organization must ensure the firm footing of the worker, allowing free movement and visual control of their activities, as well as the safe execution of labor operations.

It is necessary to provide designated places for fastening protective devices for employees who perform work on the upper parts of the aircraft glider. In the organization of workplaces and workspaces at height, it is crucial to identify danger zones where people are consistently exposed to hazardous production factors or may be at risk. These hazardous areas must be marked with safety signs and labels. Power lines and electrical distributors should be de-energized in the vicinity of live or active parts of electrical equipment, especially when there is a risk of accidental contact. In such cases, a sign should be displayed on extinguishing equipment, stating, 'Do not turn on! Work is underway!' The use of metal ladders and stairs is prohibited in cases where it is not possible to turn off the voltage during work. It is also forbidden to gather people and materials in the air, on platforms, and other equipment beyond their calculated load capacity. When carrying out work at height, technological gaps, elevator shafts, and openings in barriers should be blocked or closed using barriers. Personal equipment should be stored in bags or special sorters. Workers performing tasks at height must ensure that tools, parts, or materials do not fall on individuals standing below. Protective barriers should be installed in cases where people are beneath the work area, and there is no solid floor underneath [1].

Access to outsiders should be closed and warning signs should be posted in the area where docks, basins, platforms are being installed or separated. When climbing from the ladder to the furnaces, the worker must have a safety belt and must be attached to the construction of the furnace with a chain during work.

It is allowed to climb wooden masts with a height of not more than 15 m

with the help of nails. The worker must be connected to the mast with the safety belt chain while lifting. It is necessary to use two chain protection belts to ensure safety during the transition period. When a worker is climbing a mast on a suspended crane, he must be tied to the suspended crane with a safety belt. It is necessary to raise and lower the worker at a speed not exceeding 10 minutes only with his instructions. A worker working at high altitude must be equipped with a megaphone. Worker 1.5 m. and higher than that, when working on portable ladders, it is necessary to fasten the protective belt to a structure or pole with a spring hook.

CONCLUSION. So, in conclusion, it is forbidden to connect an unsecured ladder with a spring hook of a safety belt. Additionally, it is prohibited for two or more workers to work on the same portable ladder or on the same side of the ladder, as well as to ascend or descend the ladder simultaneously. When mobile ladders are used in areas where vehicles and people move, the ladder's installation site should be blocked or guarded during work.

When carrying out welding work at height, the platform and platform must be made of non-flammable (difficult to burn) materials. In the absence of havozi (safety nets), welders should use flame-resistant safety belts, ropes, and safety ropes with carabiners, as well as special bags for storing tools and electrode remnants.

During simultaneous work at different heights on the same vertical, the goal is to protect the employee working on the lower floor from metal fragments, sparks, and other objects that may accidentally fall.

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